

THE PROBLEM OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: The main tasks of educating children of preschool age are to develop children physically, mentally and spiritually, to receive regular education based on national and universal values, taking into account their innate abilities, interest, needs and opportunities. consists of preparation (for school).

Key words: young generation, children, physical training, physically active, movement training, general physical development.

INTRODUCTION

To protect the health of the young generation growing up in Uzbekistan, to raise them to be physically fit, agile, businessmen and to lead them to life and work. In order to implement the directive documents related to the issues of preparing for the defense of the homeland, a new approach to physical education works, being in search requires the scientific-theoretical and re-development of the practical foundations of the system. Physical development is a healing process, which is the gradual determination of changes in the functions and forms of the human body. In the growth of development, three phases can be distinguished: an increase in the level of development, relative stability, and a gradual decrease in human physical capabilities. The most vigorous development occurs in preschool and junior school age and continues throughout all periods of schooling.

Physical development is subject to objective biological laws. The most

important of these laws is the law of the unity of the environment and the development of the organism. The teacher should organize children's rest, take into account independent work and work, study conditions. All these are factors that affect the physical development of children.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

During the training, the coordination of the functioning of the organs and systems, which are working in conditions of high activity of the whole body, is improved, it is possible to find the right rhythm of work and, in connection with this, to improve the emotional state. During this period, the highest level of working ability is observed. It varies depending on the change in the description of some aspects of the activity. Physical education classes consist of three interrelated parts: introductory - physical training, the main part and the final part. Educational, educational and health-improving tasks are of great importance for each part of training. Performing these tasks provides a comprehensive impact on children.

The tasks and content of the introductory physical training part of the training can be different depending on the tasks of the first part of the physical education training and the content of the exercises in its main part. Therefore, training in one case, and entry in another case can be described as physical training.

The task of this part of the training is to create interest and emotional mood in children, to check the readiness level of attention, to clarify some movement skills, to gradually prepare the child's body for some intensive activities that will take place in the main part of the training. For this purpose, children are offered to perform familiar exercises and their variants, which help to train the correct stature, prevent flatulence, aim in space and in a team, and do not require a lot of time. Such exercises include: alignment exercises - various alignments and re-alignments; walking and running with various tasks (directed turns, change of

starters, etc.); spread out and run lightly, and then line up in large and small circles, columns, etc.; walking of various forms and for the purpose of preventing flatness - walking on the heel, tiptoe, on a thick rope on the floor, walking on a ladder and other exercises.

The introductory part ends with children lining up in groups of three or four, spreading out and so on. It serves as a transition to teach children general development exercises at the beginning of the main part of the training. This part lasts 2 to 4 minutes for small groups, 3 to 5 minutes for medium groups, and 4 to 6 minutes for large groups. If the first part of the training is planned as an introductory-preparatory part, at the beginning of it, exercises designed for the above-mentioned introductory part will be given.

However, after that, in this part of the training, general development exercises that do not require training, consisting of only repeated and varied exercises, were given.

Their task is to prepare the child's body for a slightly higher physical load in the main part of the training. In this case, complex coordinated basic movements with sufficient physical load or sports exercises of an intensive description are planned.

The main tasks of educating children of preschool age are to develop children physically, mentally and spiritually, taking into account their innate abilities, interests, needs and opportunities, to receive regular education based on national and universal values (to school) consists of preparation.

The fulfillment of the goals and tasks set for the process of development and school preparation of preschool children is controlled by this "State requirements for the education of preschool children". The state requirements define the main directions of the educational content of preschool children and the minimum requirements for their level of preparation for school, and it is recognized as a state document.

Physical upbringing and education of the young generation is defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and "National Program of Personnel Training". A child's body develops rapidly during preschool age. His nervous system, bone and muscle systems are forming rapidly. Respiratory organs improve.

It is during this period that the foundation for health and complete physical and spiritual maturity is created. This is the main goal stated in the Law "On Education" and "National Program of Personnel Training". Goal-oriented physical education has a positive effect on the mental development of children. Their knowledge of things and events in the natural environment increases, their knowledge of time and place improves, and positive aspects of their character are formed.

Great attention is paid to preschool children being polite and loving work. From an early age, children are taught the rules of behavior at home, on the street, in kindergarten, in the guest house, behavior culture, eating, dressing, undressing, walking neatly, being polite, hardworking, and appreciating the work of others. . These habits form the basis of the content of raising a child to be polite and capable of work.

One of the important indicators of children's readiness for school is their level of physical development. Children should be active according to their age, including knowing the names and rules of national games and being able to actively participate in them, running and jumping, performing age-appropriate norms, moving quickly in formation, performing training exercises. teaching is the basis of educational content that ensures the physical development of children of preschool age.

CONCLUSION

To teach to walk evenly while maintaining balance in the right direction, to climb (independently climb and descend a small ladder), to teach not to drop

objects when throwing and rolling. Developing the small muscles of the fingers, forming the skills of grasping, performing some actions and activities together with other children. Encourage children to be active. Cultivating interest is in independent action. Walking and balance exercises. Walking in the right direction, walking on the sidewalk, on a board lying on the ground. Walking up and down from a board with one end raised 15-20 cm from the floor (width 25 cm, length 1.5-2 m). Getting into and out of a box 15 cm high. Crossing with the help of adults over a drawing or board thrown on the ground and raised 15-25 cm from the floor. The process of physical and mental development of preschool children is fast. Because their body is constantly growing, they cannot sit still. But at this stage, the child's physical growth seems to slow down a little from the outside. That is, between the ages of 3 and 4, children grow by only 4 cm. Parents should pay special attention to the physical development of their children and create conditions for their free and easy movement. Because the depth of a child's thinking, the richness of his speech, and his acquisition of spiritual qualities depend primarily on his health.

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